

Ionizing radiation resistance of butadiene and silicone rubbers for Mars applications

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling editor: Dr. Jay Laverne

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to investigate the ionizing radiation resistance of Butadiene (BR) and Vinyl-Silicone (VMQ) rubbers, which are the most promising candidates for Mars applications due to their low-temperature elasticity. The influence of various fillers on BR and aromatic silicone oligomer on VMQ radiation resistance was investigated by β or γ irradiation. The irradiation was carried out at two doses of 5 kGy or 10 kGy. In general, VMQ exhibits good radiation resistance even without the addition of the aromatic silicone oligomer. In contrast, the radiation resistance of BR was improved after the incorporation of the fillers, especially of mineral origin – silica, TiO₂, or ZnO, which is probably a result of radiation interaction with the fillers' particles instead of rubber macromolecules. Both rubbers have proved to be promising elastomer bases for designing future Mars rubber compounds.

1. Introduction

Application of rubber materials in the space sector is inevitable because of their unique viscoelastic and barrier properties, making them perfect materials for seals, hoses, and inflatable elements. Still, rubber presence in deep-space critical missions, like Mars exploration, is limited. For now, no rubber material is used on Mars in applications typically employing them on Earth. For example, metal (Eaton C-seals), or polymer, e.g. spring-energized polytetrafluoroethylene seals (*Space Exploration – Aerospace & Defense*), are currently used in the construction of Mars rovers instead of traditionally used rubber seals. However, the constantly increasing weight of Mars rovers and their self-driving capabilities result in new material challenges. For example, NASA's Curiosity rover's aluminum wheels sustained significant damage due to their limited flexibility and resistance to frequent deformation (Breaks Observed in Rover). Such damage would never happen to a classic wheel equipped with a rubber tire. But the development of this kind of wheel requires rubber exclusively designed to withstand Martian conditions (Anyszka and Blume, 2021). The daily temperature amplitude on Mars is much higher than on Earth (for example, up to 110 °C of daily difference recorded by the Spirit rover (Anyszka et al., 2022b)),

and the average temperature is much lower (around –60 °C). Therefore, only the elastomers having sufficiently low glass transition temperature can be considered for the Mars rubber design. A good example of constant progress in the field of rubber materials for space is the silicone docking seal design for SpaceX's Dragon capsule (the newest crewed spacecraft (*Dragon Sending Humans*)), which is vulcanized in a big single mold to assure the best possible performance and low gas permeability (Russell, 2020).

One of the crucial aspects of the space environment is the presence of ionizing radiation, which may cause damage to the elastomer chains. Therefore, radiation resistance needs to be taken into consideration in designing rubber for extraterrestrial applications because most polymer composites, like rubber, are much more susceptible to radiation-induced damage than metals or ceramics (Shulman and Ginell, 1970). Radiation resistance of elastomers, which are the main polymeric constituent of rubber, started to be investigated alongside the development of nuclear plants, which used rubber seals in their construction. One of the first results on the radiation resistance of rubber was presented by Bopp and Sisman in 1953 summarizing the changes in physical and mechanical properties, and gas evolution of main rubber types after exposition to radiation from a graphite reactor (beta, gamma, fast-, and

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2025.113372>

Received 11 July 2025; Received in revised form 7 October 2025; Accepted 9 October 2025

Available online 10 October 2025

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thermal-neutron irradiation) (Bopp and Sisman, 1953). The results showed that predominant chain scission or cross-linking takes place in the elastomer depending on the chemical structure of its macromolecules. However, very soon it became clear that not only the chemical structure of elastomer macromolecules plays a role in radiation aging, but also various additives used in rubber compounds (Bohm and Tveekrem, 1982). Rubbers are unique polymer composites, which require a much greater amount of additives to achieve and maintain their properties than other polymer composites. Sometimes the amount of additives even exceeds the amount of elastomer in rubber compounds (Choi, 2004). Therefore, the influence of the additives on rubber radiation resistance may often play a key role. Over time, it turned out that many of the additives enhance the radiation resistance of rubber, like carbon black (Markovic et al., 2009) used as a common reinforcing filler, or zinc oxide (Borjanović et al., 2012), commonly used as a vulcanization activator. Mars does not have a magnetosphere, which results in extensive ionizing radiation reaching its surface in much higher doses than on Earth. Thus, the radiation resistance of the most temperature-resistant elastomers needs to be studied and potentially improved to ensure a satisfactory aging resistance of the Mars rubber compounds. Generally, rubber aging results in significant structural changes of the aged compound, which negatively affect its dynamic mechanical properties, leading to inevitable loss of functional properties. Aging is caused by radical reactions leading either to cross-linking or chain scission of polymer macromolecules. In this view, rubber compounds exposed to ionizing radiation are more prone to aging due to the formation of radiation-induced radicals.

BR/VMQ blends are considered to be promising elastomer bases to develop rubber withstanding Mars environmental conditions (Anyszka et al., 2022a; Zorzano et al., 2024). Therefore, their radiation resistance is important to ensure maintaining the rubber's properties during space travel and on the surface of Mars. The radiation resistance of BR (Bohm and Tveekrem, 1982) and silicone rubber (Patel et al., 2006; Di et al., 2006; Jiang et al., 2006, 2007; Diao et al., 2011; Maxwell and Balazs, 2003; Chien et al., 2000) was studied intensively in the past. However, most of the literature sources present studies that were done at high radiation doses, which exceed the levels of radiation present in space or on Mars' surface. Usually, the doses applied in the studies start at 50 kGy and can reach 1000 kGy. This is way beyond the doses that were registered by the Curiosity rover on the surface of Mars (Hassler et al., 2014), which oscillate between 190 and 220 $\mu\text{Gy}/\text{day}$ which sums up to 0.07–0.08 Gy annually. It is also known that the radiation degradation of elastomers depends on the absorbed dose (Bohm and Tveekrem, 1982; Seguchi and Morita, 1999). Therefore, in the current study, the applied radiation doses were chosen to be 5 kGy or 10 kGy as a middle ground between the literature values, which resulted in visible changes in the elastomers' structure, and the real radiation doses expected on Mars within the lifespan of the exploration rovers and equipment. With this study, it is anticipated to obtain a realistic view of the radiation resistance of BR and VMQ and their potential improvement for future Mars applications.

This work aims to investigate the radiation resistance of butadiene (BR) and vinyl-silicone (VMQ)-based rubber compounds in medium-low radiation doses of gamma and beta radiations, generated from a ^{60}Co source (gamma rays) or simulated by accelerated electrons (electron beam from an accelerator). The use of two different radiation sources allows investigating the effect of the dose rate (γ rays – slow rate, β rays – fast rate) on the chemical structure of the irradiated macromolecules. It is hypothesized that the irradiation rate is relevant when atmospheric oxygen is present in the bulk of rubber. BR compounds were filled with carbon black, silica, carbon nanotubes, ZnO, and TiO_2 , while VMQ was modified with aromatic rings-containing silicone oligomer, which was blended and co-cured with VMQ, to improve their radiation resistance.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Two elastomers were tested for radiation resistance: 1. Lithium-catalyzed Butadiene Rubber (BR) Buna® CB 550 (cis 1,4 content of 38 %, vinyl content of 9–10 %, Mooney viscosity of 54 MU – ML (1 + 4) measured at 100 °C) produced by Arlanxeo Performance Elastomers, the Netherlands; 2. Vinyl-methyl silicone rubber (VMQ) Polimer® MV 1,0 a high-vinyl content (0.135 mmol/g), high-temperature vulcanizable rubber produced by Silikony Polskie Ltd., Poland. Both elastomers were cured with Dicumyl Peroxide (DCP) of 99 % purity produced by Akrochem Corporation, Akron, Ohio, USA. VMQ was modified with aromatic groups by laboratory mixer blending at 100 °C operating with 30 rpm rotor speed for 6 min, and co-curing in a laboratory press at 150 °C under 10 MPa, with an oligomeric phenylmethylsiloxane-dimethylsiloxane copolymer (*o*-PMQ) of molecular weight of 3500–4000 g/mol and kinematic viscosity of $5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, produced by Gelest Inc., USA. The VMQ-based compounds were reinforced with 20 phr of dimethyldichlorosilane-hydrophobized fumed silica Aerosil® R972 (Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area of 90–130 m^2/g) manufactured by Evonik Industries, Germany. BR was compounded with the following fillers: 1. Carbon Black (CB) N330 grade (BET surface area of 78 m^2/g) originated from Markochem S.A., Poland; 2. Precipitated silica Zeosil® 1165 MP (BET surface area of 165 m^2/g) originated from Solvay, Belgium; 3. Titanium dioxide (TiO_2 , Anatase/Rutile, purity of 99.55+%, particle size of 18 nm) originated from Nanografi Nano Technology, Ankara, Turkey; 4. Zinc oxide (ZnO, purity of >99.99 %, particle size of 18 nm) originated from Nanografi Nano Technology, Ankara, Turkey; 5. Short-length multi-walled Carbon Nanotubes (CNT, purity of >96 %, outer diameter of 48–78 nm) originated from Nanografi Nano Technology, Ankara, Turkey.

3. Methods

The rubber compounds were mixed in a laboratory-scale mixer (Brabender Plastograph® Lab-station, Germany) equipped with tangential rotors, operating in a 70 cm^3 chamber. Unfilled VMQ exhibits very weak mechanical properties, so its vulcanizates can break apart during handling. Therefore, it was necessary to use a reinforcing filler for the VMQ compounds, allowing their further testing. For this, a hydrophobized fumed silica (Aerosil® R972) was used. The compound formulations are given in Table 1. BR-based compounds were filled with only 10 phr of fillers to avoid the reinforcing effect of filler networking on the mechanical properties of the compounds. In this way, it is easier to elucidate the effect of irradiation on the mechanical properties of the BR compounds. Also, no filler-rubber coupling agent was added for the same reason. To obtain a good reinforcement from the silica, high-temperature mixing was required. Therefore, the mixing procedures for VMQ and BR compounds are different. For BR mixing, the chamber was pre-heated to 70 °C and the temperature of the compounds was increased to 75–80 °C during mixing. VMQ mixing with *o*-PMQ consisted of two steps: 1. High-temperature incorporation of the fumed silica at 100 °C, allowing sufficient wetting of the filler surface by the rubber and oligomer macromolecules; 2. Medium-temperature incorporation of DCP at 70 °C. The mixing procedures are described in Tables 2 and 3.

The prepared compounds were vulcanized in an electrically heated (PID temperature-controlled) homemade hydraulic laboratory press (maximum pressure 20 MPa) in the form of 15 x 15 x 1.5 cm plates, at 150 °C, under 10 MPa pressure according to the vulcanization time obtained from the kinetics of vulcanization measurements. The kinetics of vulcanization were tested by means of a Rubber Process Analyzer RPA 2000 (Alpha Technologies, USA) at 150 °C with a frequency of 1.67 Hz, and a strain of 9.98 % for 30 min.

The dispersion and distribution of fillers were analyzed based on the

Table 1

Formulations of the BR and VMQ compounds presented as weight parts per hundred parts of rubber (phr).

Component (phr)	Samples denotation									
	BR	BR-CB	BR-Sil	BR-TiO ₂	BR-ZnO	BR-CNT	VMQ-100	VMQ-90/10	VMQ-80/20	VMQ-70/30
BR	100	100	100	100	100	100	–	–	–	–
VMQ	–	–	–	–	–	–	100	90	80	70
<i>o</i> -PMQ	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10	20	30
Aerosil® R972	–	–	–	–	–	–	20	20	20	20
CB N330	–	10	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Zeosil® 1165 MP	–	–	10	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
TiO ₂	–	–	–	10	–	–	–	–	–	–
ZnO	–	–	–	–	10	–	–	–	–	–
CNT	–	–	–	–	–	10	–	–	–	–
DCP	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	1	1	1	1

Table 2

Mixing procedure of the BR compounds.

Time [min:sec]	Action
0:00	Pre-heating to 70 °C [30 rpm]
0:00	Addition of BR
1:00	Addition of the filler (CB, Zeosil® 1165 MP, TiO ₂ , or ZnO)
1:30	Increasing the rotor speed to 60 rpm
3:00	Decreasing the rotor speed to 30 rpm, addition of DCP
3:30	Increasing the rotor speed to 60 rpm
5:00	Stop mixing (reaching 75–80 °C)

Table 3

Mixing procedure of the VMQ compounds.

Time [min:sec]	Action
0:00	Step 1: pre-heating to 100 °C [30 rpm]
0:00	Addition of VMQ
1:00	Addition of Aerosil® R972 and <i>o</i> -PMQ
2:30	Increasing the rotor speed to 60 rpm
6:00	Stop mixing (reaching 100–105 °C)
0:00	Step 2: pre-heating to 70 °C [30 rpm]
0:00	Addition of the pre-mix from Step 1
0:30	Addition DCP
1:00	Increasing the rotor speed to 60 rpm
2:00	Stop mixing

VMQ-100 vulcanizate, as the dispersion conditions were the most challenging among all the compounds. The VMQ exhibits significantly lower viscosity than the BR, resulting in lower shear forces implemented for filler dispersion during mixing. The silica dispersion and distribution in VMQ were analyzed by optical microscope LAB40 (Opta-Tech, Poland) at a magnification of $\times 200$ and an Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) NaoAFM (Nanosurf, Switzerland) operating in tapping mode with free vibration amplitude of 200 mV. The AFM pictures were taken at a speed of 1 line per second with 256 lines scanned in total.

The obtained vulcanizates were subjected to an electron beam (simulating β radiation) and gamma (γ) irradiation without any pre-conditioning. The β irradiation was done by means of an electron beam from a linear accelerator operating with the following parameters: 6 MeV, 4 μ s, 20 Hz, distance from accelerator window 180 cm; dose rate c. a. 3.0 kGy/min, set for 5 or 10 kGy. The samples were placed perpendicularly to the β radiation source. The gamma irradiation was done using a ⁶⁰Co radiation source operating with a dose rate of 300 Gy/h and set for 10 kGy. The samples were placed parallel to the γ radiation source. The samples were used as received from the laboratory press, without degassing. Such an approach simulates the state of rubber stored inside a habitat with a breathable oxygen-containing atmosphere.

Before and after the β and γ irradiations, the vulcanizates were tested for their mechanical tensile properties and equilibrium swelling for cross-link density. The tensile testing was done using a Tensometer 2000 device produced by Alpha Technologies, USA. This test was carried out

according to the ISO 37 standard. The measured values were moduli at 50 % (M50), 100 % (M100), 200 % (M200), and 300 % (M300) of elongation, tensile strength (Ts), and elongation at break (Eb). The equilibrium swelling of the vulcanizates, which provides information on cross-link density and sol content, was done by immersing three different-shaped samples (triangle, circular, and square) in toluene at room temperature for 7 days (with one-time solvent change after 4 days). The samples were weighed before and after swelling without prior pre-conditioning (extraction of non-crosslinked additives by a polar solvent) due to the very low amount of DCP, which was the only additive forming volatile products during curing. After the swelling, the samples were placed in a laboratory oven heated up to 50 °C overnight to remove the solvent and weighed again. This was done to calculate the vulcanizates' swelling and sol content. The tested compounds were filled with a small amount of fillers to ensure no noticeable impact of the filler-filler or filler-polymer interactions on the swelling measurements (Bernal-Ortega et al., 2024; Valentín et al., 2010). Therefore, the equilibrium swelling results can be directly related to the cross-link densities of the vulcanizates.

The equilibrium swelling Q_w was calculated according to equation (1) (Frenkel, 1940; Flory, 1953):

$$Q_w = \frac{((m_s - m_f) - (m_d - m_f))}{m_d - m_f} \quad (1)$$

where: m_s – is the weight of swollen samples, m_d – is the weight of dried samples, m_f – is the weight of filler.

The sol content represents the amount of chemically unbound polymer in the network, which can be formed as a result of the degradation of the rubber macromolecules. The sol content was calculated according to equation (2) (Baker, 1949):

$$\text{Sol content} = \frac{(m_b - m_d)}{m_b} \cdot 100\% \quad (2)$$

where: m_d – is the weight of samples before swelling, m_b – is the weight of dried samples.

The error bars of the measurements were calculated by using the least-squares method from the population of 8–10 samples for the tensile tests and 3 samples for the equilibrium swelling and sol content tests. The values were presented with an accuracy of 0.01 for the tensile stress parameters and equilibrium swelling, 0.1 for sol content, and 1 for the elongation at break.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Silica dispersion and distribution in VMQ

The optic microscopy picture of the VMQ-100 compound surface (Fig. 1) reveals that the silica forms a number of micro-sized clusters evenly distributed in the bulk of the silicone matrix. In general, silicone rubbers exhibit very low viscosity in comparison to their fully organic

Fig. 1. Silica agglomerates in the VMQ-100 sample observed by optical microscopy at magnification of $\times 200$.

counterparts, like BR, therefore, the shear forces are not high enough to disintegrate all the silica clusters during mixing. The obtained level of silica dispersion and distribution is satisfactory from the technological point of view.

To investigate further the micromorphology of the VMQ-100 compound, AFM scanning was performed in the homogeneous regions between silica clusters (Fig. 2). A cluster-free space on the surface of the VMQ-100 compound was chosen by using an optical microscope (Fig. 2a), and AFM scanning was performed by mapping three different areas (Fig. 2b–d). The AFM pictures showed a very homogeneous structure of the sample, indicating very good microdispersion of silica on the nanoscopic level.

4.2. Effect of fillers on BR radiation resistance

Polymers, including elastomers, may undergo cross-linking or scission of their backbones upon irradiation, or both processes may occur simultaneously (Bopp and Sisman, 1953; Davenas et al., 2002). These depend chiefly on the polymer chemistry and the presence of additives,

Fig. 2. Optic microscopy picture on the AFM's cantilever scanning area (a) and AFM pictures of the VMQ-100 sample micromorphology taken at three different scanning areas: $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$ (b), $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ (c), and $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ (d).

and the conditions of irradiation. For example, in the case of polyethylene, a scission of the (C–H) bond takes place predominantly in the absence of oxygen, instead of the main chain (C–C) (Partridge, 1970). This is explained by Partridge as the excitation energy transfer along the main polymer chain, preventing its scission, while the (C–H) bond is cleaved. As a result, the formation of unsaturated (C=C) bonds or cross-links by recombination of the macroradicals in an oxygen-free environment leads to hydrogen (H_2) formation. Alternatively, polymer chain scission occurs predominantly if there is a carbon atom connected to four other carbon atoms in the main chain of a polymer. In such a case the radiation-induced energy excitation can break all four bonds and the presence of side groups bigger than hydrogen decreases the possibility of re-formation of the main chain (Carlsson and Lacoste, 1991).

As a result of the performed irradiation tests in presence of oxygen, the unfilled BR-REF compound undergoes predominantly cross-linking when a higher dose rate (β rays - 3.0 kGy/min) is applied, or chain scission upon a lower dose rate (γ rays - 300 Gy/h) (Fig. 3). This results in the decrease of equilibrium swelling and increase in the M200 modulus after the β irradiation (which both indicates higher cross-link density), and oppositely, the increase in equilibrium swelling and decrease in the M200 modulus for the γ irradiated sample (which indicates lower cross-link density). Additionally, after the γ irradiation a presence of 2.6 % sol (measured as the extracted matter after the toluene-swelling of the vulcanizate) was observed, which is formed due to chain scission of the BR macromolecules. This finding is consistent with a classic view of the radiation effects in polymers, according to which the effects may depend not only on the chemistry of the polymer itself but also on the dose rate (Seguchi and Morita, 1999). Many experiments proved that the predominant effect of butadiene rubber and its copolymers (styrene-butadiene rubber, acrylonitrile-butadiene rubber) irradiation is cross-linking over chain scission, however, this greatly depends on additives present in the tested BR compound (Bohm and Tveekrem, 1982; Markovic et al., 2009). It is hypothesized that the presence of oxygen may play a crucial role in the radiation test. When the dose rate is high (β rays) the oxygen dissolved in the compounds is consumed quickly in radical reactions and there is no time for the atmospheric oxygen to diffuse into the bulk of the compounds and replace the consumed oxygen molecules. Therefore, most of the radical reactions at high radiation dose rates take place in an anaerobic environment leading to predominantly cross-linking reactions. In contrast, when a low dose rate is applied the atmospheric oxygen can diffuse into the bulk of the compounds and take part in the radical reactions leading predominantly to polymer chain scission. The oxygen-assisted mechanism of BR chain scission is presented in Scheme 1. Also, the application of higher dose rates might result in heating the samples, which

Fig. 3. Comparison of the equilibrium swelling (Q_w), sol content, modulus at 200 % of elongation (M200), and elongation at break (Eb) for the unfilled BR-REF compound before and after the irradiation tests using different radiation types and doses.

Scheme 1. Possible oxygen-assisted chain scission mechanism occurring during the γ irradiation, based on (Gijssman, 2008; Xie et al., 2019; Espino et al., 2019).

influences the kinetics of degradation of the macromolecules.

The tensile properties of the BR-based filled compounds are presented in Table 4, while the swelling results are in Table 5. Additionally, relative changes in Ts, Eb, M100, and Qw for the BR-based compounds are shown in Figs. 4–7, respectively. The results in the Figures present mechanical and swelling parameters before and after irradiation. The column “before irradiation” is kept to present the error bars for the measurements done on non-irradiated samples.

The obtained results show that adding any studied filler (zinc oxide, titanium dioxide, silica, carbon black, or carbon nanotubes) improves the compounds’ radiation resistance. However, the best radiation improvement is observed for the compounds filled with mineral fillers – silica, TiO₂, and ZnO. This is visible in the stabilization of the mechanical parameters’ values. Especially, elongation at break values remains within the error bars for all the filled compounds after the irradiation, in contrast to the γ -irradiated BR-REF compound for which the value of this parameter is doubled (Fig. 3). This shows that the fillers are especially effective against the low-dose-rate radiation (γ treatment). It is known from the literature that the addition of CB results in an improved γ radiation resistance. For example, in 2009, Markovic et al. observed this improvement by adding an N550 CB grade into Ethylene-Propylene-Diene-Monomer Rubber/Chlorosulfonated polyethylene (EPDM/CSM) and Chloroprene Rubber/Chlorosulfonated polyethylene (CR/CSM) blends (Markovic et al., 2009). They explained this improvement by the

good filler-rubber interactions that preserve the compounds’ properties and in this way mask the effects of irradiation damage of the rubber macromolecules.

It is also known from the work of Baccaro et al. that CB interacts with γ rays, which results in the formation of free radicals inside the CB particles (Baccaro et al., 2003). The free radicals concentration increases up to a maximum dose of 500 kGy. Based on this, it can be speculated that a significant fraction of the radiation interacts with the CB particles instead of rubber molecules. In this view, CB particles act as a diluent of the polymer phase by occupying a certain volume in the rubber compound, which is much more inert to radiation damage than rubber macromolecules. The bulk of filler particles solely do not contribute to rubber’s mechanical properties in contrast to its surface; therefore, the potential radiation damage of the bulk of filler particles does not affect the overall rubber’s performance. This can lead to improved radiation resistance of the CB-filled compounds since radiation interactions with the bulk CB particles do not affect the polymer network. A similar effect was reported for silica by Patel et al. (2006). They reported the formation of paramagnetic species in silica as an effect of γ irradiation, which are generated above the irradiation dose of 1 kGy. It was also shown that most of such paramagnetic species at relatively low doses of irradiation (up to 20 kGy) stay trapped inside the bulk of silica. Here again one may speculate that because of the presence of silica, the BR macromolecules interact less frequently with the high energy rays, which results in better

Table 4

Mechanical properties of the BR compounds before and after irradiation. The table contains values of moduli at 50 % (M50), 100 % (M100), 200 % (M200), and 300 % (M300) of elongation, tensile strength (Ts), and elongation at break (Eb).

Parameter	Samples denotation					
	BR-REF	BR-CB	BR-Sil	BR-TiO ₂	BR-ZnO	BR-CNT
Before irradiation						
M50 (MPa)	0.57 ± 0.04	1.07 ± 0.11	1.41 ± 0.11	0.80 ± 0.05	0.68 ± 0.03	0.66 ± 0.06
M100 (MPa)	0.82 ± 0.04	1.35 ± 0.12	1.95 ± 0.11	1.07 ± 0.06	0.96 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.04
M200 (MPa)	1.15 ± 0.12	1.91 ± 0.24	–	1.46 ± 0.07	1.35 ± 0.08	1.15 ± 0.05
M300 (MPa)	–	–	–	–	–	1.42 ± 0.08
Ts (MPa)	1.20 ± 0.18	2.66 ± 0.20	2.58 ± 0.28	1.46 ± 0.10	1.43 ± 0.14	2.10 ± 0.12
Eb (%)	213 ± 38	290 ± 57	150 ± 30	204 ± 20	224 ± 21	626 ± 63
β 5 kGy						
M50 (MPa)	0.54 ± 0.03	1.11 ± 0.09	1.36 ± 0.11	0.72 ± 0.09	0.72 ± 0.04	0.79 ± 0.04
M100 (MPa)	0.84 ± 0.04	1.44 ± 0.14	1.86 ± 0.32	1.04 ± 0.09	1.03 ± 0.03	1.00 ± 0.04
M200 (MPa)	1.27 ± 0.09	1.99 ± 0.08	–	1.45 ± 0.11	1.46 ± 0.04	1.27 ± 0.09
M300 (MPa)	–	–	–	–	–	1.58 ± 0.13
Ts (MPa)	1.48 ± 0.16	2.35 ± 0.23	2.60 ± 0.25	1.52 ± 0.12	1.49 ± 0.11	2.38 ± 0.10
Eb (%)	236 ± 27	237 ± 45	157 ± 25	210 ± 11	206 ± 19	636 ± 112
β 10 kGy						
M50 (MPa)	0.57 ± 0.05	1.04 ± 0.07	1.57 ± 0.12	0.86 ± 0.09	0.71 ± 0.03	0.86 ± 0.07
M100 (MPa)	0.87 ± 0.04	1.33 ± 0.08	2.19 ± 0.21	1.10 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.03	1.11 ± 0.06
M200 (MPa)	1.22 ± 0.08	1.81 ± 0.13	–	–	–	1.44 ± 0.08
M300 (MPa)	–	–	–	–	–	1.82 ± 0.12
Ts (MPa)	1.36 ± 0.13	2.37 ± 0.32	2.71 ± 0.20	1.39 ± 0.09	1.42 ± 0.11	2.53 ± 0.14
Eb (%)	229 ± 29	269 ± 38	145 ± 21	178 ± 34	190 ± 21	503 ± 63
γ 10 kGy						
M50 (MPa)	0.50 ± 0.04	1.01 ± 0.08	1.34 ± 0.17	0.80 ± 0.11	0.69 ± 0.06	0.80 ± 0.04
M100 (MPa)	0.71 ± 0.03	1.31 ± 0.10	1.80 ± 0.09	1.09 ± 0.07	0.99 ± 0.04	1.04 ± 0.03
M200 (MPa)	0.96 ± 0.03	1.78 ± 0.11	–	–	1.32 ± 0.02	1.32 ± 0.03
M300 (MPa)	1.20 ± 0.07	–	–	–	–	1.63 ± 0.04
Ts (MPa)	1.56 ± 0.24	2.48 ± 0.14	2.80 ± 0.23	1.44 ± 0.14	1.33 ± 0.06	2.38 ± 0.02
Eb (%)	431 ± 70	278 ± 29	191 ± 40	193 ± 38	200 ± 25	545 ± 25

Table 5
Equilibrium swelling and sol content of the BR compounds before and after irradiation.

Parameter	Samples denotation					
	BR-REF	BR-CB	BR-Sil	BR-TiO ₂	BR-ZnO	BR-CNT
Before irradiation						
Q _w (-)	4.69 ± 0.22	6.10 ± 0.21	3.01 ± 0.02	3.89 ± 0.02	4.25 ± 0.05	8.72 ± 0.25
Sol content (%)	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	11.8 ± 0.4
β 5 kGy						
Q _w (-)	4.26 ± 0.10	6.04 ± 0.05	3.03 ± 0.03	4.17 ± 0.15	4.04 ± 0.02	8.16 ± 0.34
Sol content (%)	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	10.3 ± 1.0
β 10 kGy						
Q _w (-)	4.52 ± 0.07	6.90 ± 0.32	3.06 ± 0.02	3.97 ± 0.04	4.08 ± 0.07	6.83 ± 0.07
Sol content (%)	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	9.5 ± 0.3
γ 10 kGy						
Q _w (-)	5.46 ± 0.04	7.03 ± 0.18	3.15 ± 0.05	4.06 ± 0.07	4.09 ± 0.05	6.88 ± 0.74
Sol content (%)	2.6 ± 0.2	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0.7 ± 0.5	8.5 ± 1.6

Fig. 4. Changes in tensile strength (Ts) in relation to the compounds before the irradiation for the BR-based compounds.

Fig. 6. Changes in modulus at 100 % of elongation (M100) in relation to the compounds before the irradiation for the BR-based compounds.

Fig. 5. Changes in elongation at break (Eb) in relation to the compounds before the irradiation for the BR-based compounds.

Fig. 7. Changes in equilibrium swelling (Qw) in relation to the compounds before the irradiation for the BR-based compounds.

radiation resistance of the BR-Sil compound.

Nanometric TiO₂ (Di et al., 2006) and ZnO (Bojanovic et al., 2012) are reported in the literature to improve silicone rubber's proton radiation resistance. The mechanism of ZnO action is discussed in view of its interaction with ionizing rays and its ability to quench structural defects caused by irradiation. It is described in literature as a "hard radiation" material, meaning that it can resist radiation environment very well (Bojanovic et al., 2012). The current study shows that the addition of TiO₂ or ZnO also improves the β and γ radiation resistance of BR. This effect is probably also a consequence of the particles' interaction with

the ionizing β or γ rays, which statistically reduces the number of polymer chain interactions with the high-energy rays.

The addition of carbon nanotubes (CNT) is reported in the literature to improve the radiation resistance of silicone rubber (Bojanovic et al., 2012), poly (methyl methacrylate) (Tatro et al., 2004), polyimide (Nielsen et al., 2008), or polyacrylonitrile (Chae et al., 2006). It was noticed that the presence of CNT suppresses the number of free radicals formed after γ irradiation, due to its good radical-scavenging capacity (Nielsen et al., 2008). Thus, it reduces the number of free radicals in the system, whose presence leads to the degradation of polymer

macromolecules. In the current study, the addition of CNT results in an improvement in the radiation resistance of BR in comparison to the unfilled compounds. However, there is a noticeable cross-linking occurring in the irradiated BR-CNT samples, which can be seen in the decreasing Qw (Fig. 7) and sol content (Table 5) with increasing radiation dose. Also, the M100 parameter noticeably increases indicating that new cross-link formation takes place (Fig. 6). Contrary to BR-CNT, the BR-CB compound undergoes degradation after irradiation, which is visible in the increased equilibrium swelling of the BR-CB compound after 10 kGy of β or γ irradiation (Fig. 7). This suggests a much stronger antioxidative effect of CNTs in BR, in comparison to CB, which suppresses the oxygen-assisted chain scission mechanism (Scheme 1). This is in line with the literature suggesting a strong antioxidative character of CNTs (Guan et al., 2018). For example, Wang et al. studied the oxidative degradation of NBR filled with CB and additional CNTs (Wang et al., 2024). The results showed that the addition of 2 phr of CNTs into an NBR compound already containing 50 phr of CB increased significantly its resistance to oxidation aging. Aging coefficient increased to 0.80 from 0.71 and to 0.74 from 0.58 after 2 and 5 days of the NBR compounds' aging, respectively.

The predominant effect of chain scission over cross-linking for CB-filled rubber was also observed by Markovic et al. (2009). In the current study, the progressing chains scission does not result in sol formation (Table 3). This might be explained by the ability of CB aggregates to trap rubber molecules as "occluded rubber" within the aggregates (Medalia, 1970). These types of physically trapped rubber macromolecules cannot be washed out in a simple swelling test at room temperature. Therefore, they are not visible as sol even after their cleavage as a result of irradiation. A bound rubber molecule can be cleaved by irradiation in the vicinity of a CB aggregate, where both parts are still bound on the filler's surface.

Two more effects of the fillers' addition should be considered. Firstly, the incorporation of CB, CNT, and silica results in improved mechanical properties, even though the amount of the fillers was set low enough not to exceed the reinforcing percolation threshold, which determines the minimum amount of filler required to form a reinforcing network in the rubber matrix (Sahakaro, 2017). The observed reinforcement is expressed by a significant increase in Ts and Eb (for the CB and CNT-filled vulcanizates), which go beyond values achieved solely by the hydrodynamic effect (Domurath et al., 2017). This may be explained by good polymer-filler interactions, which contribute to the reinforcement of the compounds. CB is known to be able to interact with rubber macromolecules, forming a tightly bonded rubber shell around CB particles. The exact nature of these interactions is complex and under constant investigation, but it practically results in a visible reinforcement of rubber. It is generalized that the majority of CB-rubber interaction is based on physical interactions, which are, however, accompanied by covalent bonds formed, for example, during compounding or vulcanization (Robertson and Hardman, 2021). De Falco et al. reported that the addition of even very small amounts of CB can result in a visible mechanical reinforcement of styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR) (De Falco et al., 2007). They added only 0.66 wt% of CB into SBR compounds, which resulted in a noticeable increase in the tensile strength and moduli of the compounds. CB is also an effective filler for polar rubbers as reported by Gyung-Hyun et al. who concluded that with an increasing CB content the mobility of Nitrile-Butadiene Rubber (NBR) chains decreases, suggesting the formation of bound rubber (Kim et al., 2021), while Husnan et al. reported improvement in mechanical properties of CB-filled NBR (Husnan et al., 2018).

Regarding the effect of silica addition, it is reported in the literature that incorporation of as low as 10 phr of fumed or precipitated silica can result in a visible improvement of the mechanical properties of rubber (Prasertsri and Rattanasom, 2012). This is in line with the results presented in the current study. The tensile strength of the BR-Sil sample is one of the highest compared among all the compounds, the moduli are the highest, while the Eb is the lowest (Table 2).

The second effect is the decrease in cross-link density for the compounds filled with CB and CNT visible in the highest values of their equilibrium swelling (Table 5). This is most likely a result of radical scavenging actions of both CB (Allen et al., 1998) and CNT (Shimizu et al., 2020), which reduce the number of free radicals formed by DCP and effectively decrease the cross-link density.

4.3. Effect of aromatic groups on VMQ radiation resistance

The VMQ compounds were filled with dimethyldichlorosilane-hydrophobized fumed silica for reinforcement, blended and co-cured with the phenylmethylsiloxane-dimethylsiloxane copolymer (*o*-PMQ) using DCP to incorporate phenyl rings into the rubber network. Phenyl rings are known in the literature as functional groups improving the radiation resistance of polymers (Di et al., 2006; Jiang et al., 2006, 2007). The prepared compounds were irradiated similarly to the BR compounds using β and γ rays.

The results of mechanical properties and swelling for the VMQ-based compounds are presented in Tables 6 and 7, respectively. Relative changes in Ts, Eb, and M50 for the VMQ-based compounds are shown in Figs. 8–10, respectively. Additionally, changes in Qw and sol content for the VMQ-based compounds are presented in Figs. 11 and 12.

Incorporation of the aromatic rings into the VMQ compounds network by adding the oligomeric phenylmethylsiloxane-dimethylsiloxane copolymer (*o*-PMQ) has a negative impact on the tensile properties of the rubber compounds (Table 6) and influences significantly swelling and sol content by reducing the cross-link density and increasing the sol content, respectively (Table 7). This stems from the reduction of cross-link density of the compounds with an increasing amount of *o*-PMQ (Table 7), which is caused by the difference in molecular weight between the oligomeric *o*-PMQ and polymeric VMQ. With the same amount of DCP and increasing *o*-PMQ content the cross-link density of the compounds decreases, which is visible in the increasing Qw and Eb while Ts decreases (Fig. 11, Tables 6 and 7). Also, the sol content increases with increasing *o*-PMQ content, which replaces VMQ in the formulations (Fig. 12), it is assumed that the amount of DCP is not high enough to connect all the *o*-PMQ and VMQ molecules into one network. To facilitate more effective cross-linking, a higher amount of DCP should be added to the compounds containing *o*-PMQ.

Literature sources reported substantial radiation resistance in silicone polymers after the incorporation of aromatic groups (Jiang et al.,

Table 6

Mechanical properties of the VMQ compounds before and after irradiation. The table contains values of moduli at 50 % (M50), and 100 % (M100) of elongation, tensile strength (Ts), and elongation at break (Eb).

Parameter	Samples denotation			
	VMQ-100	VMQ-90/10	VMQ-80/20	VMQ-70/30
Before irradiation				
M50 (MPa)	1.45 ± 0.19	1.21 ± 0.16	1.07 ± 0.15	0.87 ± 0.08
M100 (MPa)	–	1.82 ± 0.08	1.71 ± 0.09	1.17 ± 0.11
Ts (MPa)	2.57 ± 0.35	2.09 ± 0.43	1.79 ± 0.19	1.43 ± 0.08
Eb (%)	98 ± 11	110 ± 25	106 ± 11	151 ± 31
β 5 kGy				
M50 (MPa)	1.42 ± 0.26	1.12 ± 0.22	0.93 ± 0.07	0.77 ± 0.07
M100 (MPa)	–	1.83 ± 0.25	1.59 ± 0.13	1.10 ± 0.07
Ts (MPa)	2.65 ± 0.67	2.42 ± 0.19	1.86 ± 0.30	1.45 ± 0.10
Eb (%)	98 ± 39	130 ± 14	127 ± 30	173 ± 26
β 10 kGy				
M50 (MPa)	1.50 ± 0.21	0.95 ± 0.17	1.03 ± 0.11	0.82 ± 0.10
M100 (MPa)	–	1.69 ± 0.23	1.61 ± 0.09	1.09 ± 0.04
Ts (MPa)	2.54 ± 0.32	2.29 ± 0.37	1.84 ± 0.15	1.46 ± 0.13
Eb (%)	89 ± 18	137 ± 31	128 ± 19	193 ± 37
γ 10 kGy				
M50 (MPa)	1.68 ± 0.24	1.14 ± 0.18	1.05 ± 0.13	0.71 ± 0.07
M100 (MPa)	–	1.97 ± 0.21	1.62 ± 0.13	1.06 ± 0.09
Ts (MPa)	2.26 ± 0.38	2.33 ± 0.32	1.87 ± 0.18	1.48 ± 0.14
Eb (%)	72 ± 13	117 ± 18	119 ± 26	205 ± 61

Table 7

Equilibrium swelling and sol content of the VMQ compounds before and after irradiation.

Parameter	Samples denotation			
	VMQ-100	VMQ-90/10	VMQ-80/20	VMQ-70/30
Before irradiation				
Q _w (-)	1.43 ± 0.01	1.70 ± 0.02	1.90 ± 0.01	2.23 ± 0.01
Sol content (%)	2.8 ± 0.2	9.7 ± 0.1	17.4 ± 0.3	24.9 ± 0.1
β 5 kGy				
Q _w (-)	1.49 ± 0.03	1.67 ± 0.02	1.97 ± 0.01	2.30 ± 0.04
Sol content (%)	3.1 ± 0.5	10.0 ± 0.6	17.6 ± 0.1	25.1 ± 0.3
β 10 kGy				
Q _w (-)	1.42 ± 0.03	1.64 ± 0.02	1.92 ± 0.01	2.46 ± 0.08
Sol content (%)	2.9 ± 0.2	9.2 ± 0.3	17.7 ± 0.3	25.2 ± 0.3
γ 10 kGy				
Q _w (-)	1.42 ± 0.01	1.66 ± 0.02	1.91 ± 0.02	2.41 ± 0.09
Sol content (%)	2.9 ± 0.2	9.1 ± 0.4	17.7 ± 0.1	24.8 ± 0.5

Fig. 8. Changes in tensile strength (Ts) in relation to the compounds before the irradiation for the VMQ-based compounds.

Fig. 9. Changes in elongation at break (Eb) in relation to the compounds before the irradiation for the VMQ-based compounds.

2006, 2007; Diao et al., 2011). However, in this study, the irradiation does not affect the mechanical properties, sol content, and equilibrium swelling of the VMQ-based compounds regardless of the *o*-PMQ addition, except for 10 kGy β or γ irradiation of VMQ-70/30 compound, which exhibits a slight increase in the Q_w parameter suggesting degradation of the macromolecules, (Fig. 11). The level of irradiation applied in the cited references (Di et al., 2006; Jiang et al., 2006, 2007) that is necessary to observe the cross-linking effect in silicone rubber compounds ranges from 300 to 1000 kGy of γ rays, which exceeds

Fig. 10. Changes in modulus at 50% of elongation (M50) in relation to the compounds before the irradiation for the VMQ-based compounds.

Fig. 11. Changes in equilibrium swelling (Q_w) for the VMQ-based compounds.

Fig. 12. Changes in sol content for the VMQ-based compounds.

significantly the levels used in the current study. It is also known from the literature that radiation degradation of polymers may depend on the applied dose (Bohm and Tveekrem, 1982). Also, it is reported that γ irradiation affects the interactions between silicone macromolecules and silanol groups on the silica surface leading to softening of the compound in the air atmosphere, while an opposite effect is observed in the vacuum (Maxwell and Balazs, 2003; Chien et al., 2000). In the current study, 20 phr of reinforcing silica was added to the studied compounds. Therefore, this could be the effect contributing to the softening observed in the

VMQ-70/30 compound after the irradiation. Moreover, Z. Jiang et al. reported that aromatic additives incorporated into silicone rubber only physically, without chemical bonding to the rubber macromolecules do not improve its radiation resistance (Jiang et al., 2006). They postulated that chemical bonding is necessary to effectively transfer the radiation energy absorbed by the rubber macromolecules to the aromatic groups where it can be dissipated. In this light, it seems probable that the VMQ-70/30 compound exhibiting the lowest cross-link density is not able to effectively use the aromatic groups of *o*-PMQ for energy dissipation, which leads to a slight rubber network degradation in the VMQ-70/30 compound.

5. Conclusions

In general, the radiation resistance of BR and VMQ was found very good within the applied doses (5 or 10 kGy), which are much higher than the expected radiation level on Mars (0.07–0.08 Gy annually). BR is more susceptible to low dose rate (γ) than high dose rate (β) rays in an oxidative atmosphere, which results in a predominant chain scission of its macromolecules. This can be related to the presence of oxygen in the sample, which reduces the cross-linking probability and typically induces chain degradation. During the electron beam irradiation, oxygen dissolved in a polymer is consumed quickly, and no diffusion is possible within the time of irradiation of several minutes. On the contrary, during lengthy gamma irradiation, oxygen diffuses to the sample continuously and irradiation is considered to be conducted in excess of oxygen. This is relevant for all the rubber materials, which will be used or stored indoors in the Mars habitats, where a breathable atmosphere is needed for the astronauts.

The addition of just 10 phr of any of the tested fillers effectively diminishes this weakness. All of the fillers applied for BR improve its radiation resistance, but the best effects are provided by mineral-based silica, TiO₂, and ZnO. The mechanism of this improvement is most likely caused by the rays' interaction with the fillers instead of the rubber macromolecules, as the fillers' particles occupy a certain volume in the compound, effectively decreasing the probability of interactions between rays and rubber macromolecules. The addition of CB improves BR radiation resistance but also leads to a slight predominant chain scission of its macromolecules after irradiation, which is in opposition to the use of CNT, which results in a predominant cross-linking of BR macromolecules. The action of the carbon-based fillers is most likely linked to their interaction with free radicals generated on BR macromolecules after irradiation. This property also results in less efficient peroxide cross-linking of the BR compounds filled with CB or CNT. VMQ radiation resistance is very good within the applied irradiation levels. The application of *o*-PMQ in place of VMQ does not visibly improve it, moreover, at the highest concentration (VMQ-70/30) it even decreases the resistance slightly, most likely due to the decreasing amount of cross-links, which makes the rubber network less efficient in dispersing the absorbed radiation. Possibly, an increase in the cross-link density of the VMQ compounds containing *o*-PMQ could further improve their radiation resistance by facilitating an effective distribution of the absorbed energy to the aromatic groups, where it could be dissipated.

Nonetheless, all the studied compounds exhibit very good radiation resistance based on the relatively low changes in their mechanical properties and rubber network after the applied irradiation. This proves that both rubber types are promising bases for designing rubber compounds for future Mars' environment utilization. Future work will be focused on completing BR and VMQ formulations to obtain rubber compounds of optimized properties and scaling up the process to produce functional elements that can be finally tested for their radiation resistance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Rafal Anyszka: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft,

Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Piotr Szajerski:** Supervision, Resources. **Radoslaw Wach:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Anke Blume:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

I declare no conflict of interest regarding this paper.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by the European Union Marie Skłodowska Curie Action: Global Fellowship. Grant No. 101025756.

The authors would like to thank Arlanxeo Performance Elastomers (The Netherlands), Silikony Polskie Ltd. (Poland), for providing the polymer samples, and Evonik Industries (Germany) for providing the silica.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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